

DETERMINING THE IMPACT OF REWARDS AND COMPENSATION ON EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT WORKING IN THE LIBYAN CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY

RABIA S. AJEEB ABDALLA

The High Institute for Engineering Professions, Almajurie, Benghazi city, Libya.
Email: rabia.abdalla1986@gmail.com

JOUDA R. JOUDA HAMAD

Faculty of Natural Resources and Environmental Sciences, Al-Qubba Branch, University of Derna, Libya.

ABDULKARIM OMRAN GEBRIL

Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Economic, University of Benghazi, Al-Abyar Branch, Libya.

ABDELNASER OMRAN

Libyan Academy for Postgraduate Studies, Ajdabiya city, Libya.

Abstract

Employee engagement requires compensation and benefits, which are essential prerequisites. This involves both monetary rewards and intangible benefits, like recognition and other perks. The purpose of this study is to ascertain how rewards and remuneration affect employee engagement in the Libyan construction industry. The instrument for gathering data was a standardized questionnaire, which was given to 400 people at random in the chosen study area. However, only 310 of the 400 questionnaires that were distributed were actually retrieved, yielding a response rate of 77.5%. The statistical analysis software SPSS (version 23.0) was used to perform a range of statistical analyses. The findings show that rewards and compensation have a considerable positive impact on employee engagement, which in turn has a significant beneficial effect on project management success.

Keywords: Employee, Engagement, Reward, Compensation, Construction industry, Libya.

1. INTRODUCTION

Employee engagement is frequently portrayed as something offered by the employee who can benefit the business through duty and devotion, support, optional exertion, employing skills without regard for prospective constraints, and being confident in the organization's goals and features (Tian & Robertson, 2019). Given that it is a concept that has developed through time, engagement has been defined in multiple, often competing, ways across the literature, to the point where it has become unclear to many and it is rare to find two people who define engagement in the same manner (Macey & Schneider, 2018). Employee engagement is a complicated concept, and many factors can influence the level of engagement of employees. Being that there is no "pack" that works for all organizations, there are many different strategies to foster engagement. The path to compelling engagement was formed in the adaptability of the methodology best suited for each particular firm, even though each organization may ultimately define employee engagement in an unanticipated way (Thakur, 2014). There is an

absence of adequate writing on what could be the difficulties that trap pioneers' push to enhance their employee engagement scores (Markos & Sridevi, 2010). There are employees who do not feel esteemed and associated with the activity, the purpose behind such circumstances ought to be distinguished. Human resource professionals believe that how an employee feels about participating in a particular function and how they are treated inside the company have a significant impact on their level of engagement. It has a lot to do with feelings that are generally associated with motivating primary goal achievement in an organization. No matter how hard HR and line managers work to support them, there will always be people who don't put forth their best efforts. However, in general, employees need to resolve to organizations because doing so satisfies an amazing and essential need to be a part of and contribute to something significant (Bandura, 2018). Prior research has generally agreed that a project manager's contribution to the achievement of project objectives and expectations is significant (Kerzner, 2019). As a result, "project manager" has traditionally been considered one of the most crucial factors in project management success (Loufrani-Fedida & Missonier, 2015). In addition to increasing the likelihood of project success, a competent and successful project manager also contributes to the success of the project management process (Meredith & Mantel, 2021). This study is essential for enhancing the need for employee involvement and determining its relationship to successful project management in the aforementioned areas. In connection to the above issue proclamation, the destinations of this examination are to discover the parts of employee engagement, and the segments of organizational execution, and to ponder the connections between employee engagement and project management success.

Most of the past studies had focused on using some variables that have either positive or negative influence on employee engagement towards project management success within the context of human resources management and practice at a global level (Omran, Hammad & Pakir, 2011; Omran & Zaid, 2014; Omran & Jarmajo, 2015). However, this study is only focusing on using one variable to examine its relationship with employee engagement and more focus on the construction industry within the Libyan context. According to a study by Gupta & Shukla (2018), India's construction industry is an important one to monitor for employee engagement. Lee and Ok (2018) conducted research that looked at job engagement, employee self-evaluation, and the organizational work environment in the US. Mohd Nasurdin et al. (2020) carried out a study in Malaysia to determine the association between service-oriented corporate citizenship behaviour and human resource management practices. The main aim of this study is to determine the impact of rewards and compensation on employee engagement working in the construction sector. To manage the traditional project iron triangle in terms of time, quality, and cost and to achieve the goals of project management success, project managers unquestionably need technical skills and talent.

2. PAST STUDIES

2.1 Employee engagement

Employee engagement is a complicated idea, and many factors can affect how engaged employees are. As a result, there are numerous strategies to encourage engagement, and no

single strategy works for all businesses. Although each organization may have its own definition of employee engagement, the flexibility of strategy that works best for each particular company eventually serves as the foundation for effective engagement (Thakur, 2014). Employee engagement has become a trending topic in practitioner research, as per Karatepe & Demir (2020) in academic organizational behavior study. There is not enough information in the literature about potential obstacles facing leaders trying to raise employee engagement levels (Markos & Sridevi, 2010). There are certain employees who do not feel appreciated or engaged in their work; the cause of this scenario needs to be determined. The engagement challenge, according to HR professionals, is greatly influenced by how a person feels about their employment and how they are treated by management. It has a lot to do with emotions, which are intrinsically linked to driving a company's bottom line to success. Most employees desire employment because it satisfies a strong and fundamental desire to be a part of and contribute to something worthwhile (Bhawani, 2018). Of course, there will always be some people who do not put forth their best efforts, no matter how hard HR and line managers try to encourage them. According to McEwe & Boyd (2018), employee engagement is a function of how they view and assess their company, the organization's leaders, the work itself, and the surroundings. Job resources, the importance of job resources, and personal resources have all been shown by Bakker and Demerouti (2018) to be important factors in determining work engagement. Anitha (2014) asserts that leadership, teamwork, relationships among coworkers, training, career advancement, and salary all have an impact on employee engagement. Organizational policies, processes, structures, systems, and workplace welfare are further essential characteristics. Managers should pay attention to staff abilities, knowledge, and talent, according to Echols' (2015) advice if they want to have an impact on employee engagement. According to Echols, high project management performance is driven by people who are aware of their strengths and how they fit with their talents. According to Storm and Rothmann (2003), work engagement is demonstrated through energy, contentment, involvement, and efficacy. Swaminathan and Rajasekaran (2010) asserted that engagement happens when enjoyment, motivation, and effectiveness come together.

Employee engagement requires compensation and benefits, which are essential prerequisites with monetary remuneration and non-cash incentives like praise and recognition; it often includes extras like on-site childcare, employee assistance programs, travel discounts, extended holidays, subsidized cafeterias, and other benefits. The level of employee engagement is determined by how enticing their pay and benefits are (Anitha, 2014). According to SET (Saks, 2018), after obtaining the aforementioned rewards and recognition, employees are obliged to respond with higher levels of engagement. Particularly when compensation is based on project management performance, top performers want to be distinctively acknowledged and rewarded for the great work they accomplish (Saudah & Azis, 2019; Omran et al., 2011). On the other hand, employees may experience job burnout as a result of inadequate compensation (Leiter & Maslaeh, 2016). The idea of employee engagement, as per Markos & Sridevi (2020), was built on earlier concepts including job satisfaction, employee loyalty, and corporate citizenship behavior. Employees who actively pursue their jobs and are emotionally engaged to their employers go the extra mile in terms of their terms of employment to aid in the success of their

employers. The findings of the Attridge (2019) study indicate that work engagement can be increased by workplace mental health approaches that target supervisory communication, resource support, job design, working environment, corporate culture, and leadership style. Welbourne (2017) outlined three requirements for employee engagement, the first of which is that leaders must be motivated and successful in both their core and non-core responsibilities. Second, leaders must explain in detail how each role contributes to the success of the company's strategy and plan.

Finally, leaders need to remove obstacles to employees working in non-core job responsibilities and foster a climate where those jobs are valued. Leadership, engaging managers, employee voice, and integrity are the four main enablers of employee engagement (MacLeod & Clarke, 2011). Finding and keeping talent is important for an organization's capacity to increase profitability, control expenses, grow through acquisitions, innovate, create new goods and services, and identify new markets (Rama Devi, 2019). Employee engagement is facilitated by corporate cultures that value collaboration, attractive working environments, considerate treatment of employees, opportunities for growth, flexible scheduling, and effective leadership and management techniques.

2.2 Rewards and Compensation

All benefits direct and indirect, intrinsic and extrinsic that an employee considers valuable as a result of their employment connection are referred to as rewards. The classic incentive components that make up the levers that businesses can use to inspire, engage, and retain employees include pay, benefits, learning and development, and working environment (Armstrong, 2018). Reward was developed as a tool to help companies achieve their most important objectives, which are to attract, retain, motivate, and engage people. This is accomplished via ways other than wage hikes, golden handcuffs, and other conventional ones. But also in a more effective manner that can yield lasting effects. Advantages such as incentives, various bonuses, and performance bonuses may be included in the monetary compensation when offering monetary compensation. When employees fulfill the goals or targets that their employers have set for them, they are recognized and rewarded. Rewards don't have to be monetary; for example, a paid vacation for two persons could suffice. Compensation management, regardless of the size of the organization, is one of the most difficult aspects of being a human resource professional. Compensation experts in the human resources department have issues in determining the right pay and benefits that recognize and reward employees for their contributions to the company.

Reward is aimed at maximizing the beneficial effects that a variety of rewards can have on motivation, organizational commitments, job engagement, and job satisfaction (Manus and Graham, 2013). According to Cascio (2010), there have been three significant shifts in company pay and benefits policies. This may require the implementation of initiatives for the promotion and reward of project management success, which makes pay more variable. Others may include a reduced focus on the pay position of competitors in favor of what is affordable by the company, a greater willingness to downsize the workforce size, outsource jobs, and restrict pay in order to control costs of benefits and wages/salaries.

Rewards extend beyond the definitions of compensation, remuneration, and benefits terminology, which focus on pay and other agreements with monetary values; it has transcended to almost anything that could be interpreted to mean a return to employees for displaying desirable behavior, from employee involvement in decision-making to a cash bonus or health care benefit, increased role responsibility, autonomy, access to more interesting work, and other factors that relates to the employee's quality of life. The best management tool in existence is a reward system (Rehman, Khan, and Lashari, 2020; Allen & Kilmann, 2001). Reward and incentive systems are essential in increasing capacities and converting established capacities into greater motivation and engagements, according to a UNDP research published in 2018. The article makes the case that an engagement- and reward-based policy with a financial element would draw management talent by offering incentives that inspire a bigger set of employees.

These benefits may be granted in a variety of ways, including stock options, profit-sharing plans, and recognition programs, among others. Profit sharing, according to Lusthaus & Peterson (2002), is a tactic for allocating a pool of funds for employee distribution by taking a predetermined portion of a company's profits. This program's goal is to give employees recognition for their contributions to the company's attained profit target. Higher productivity and lower employee turnover are just two examples of how devoted employees give businesses important competitive advantages. Therefore, according to Vance (2018), it is not unexpected that businesses of all sizes and types have made significant investments in the policies and procedures that encourage employee engagement and dedication. Despite the fact that engagement is defined differently among businesses, some common elements emerge. These themes include how much people believe in what they do, how satisfied employees are with their jobs how proud they are of their employers, and how much employees believe their employers value what they have to offer. The more engaged a worker is, the more likely they are to "go the extra mile" and manage extraordinary projects while on the job. Additionally, motivated employees may be more devoted to remaining with their current employers. It is obvious that dedication and involvement have the ability to result in positive business outcomes for a company (Vance, 2018).

The term "reward" refers to a broad topic that is constantly evolving. According to Bloom and Milkovich (1996), it is a "bundle of returns offered in exchange for a cluster of employee contributions." This is a vague concept that offers no insight into the potential structure of returns or the potential role that employees might play in generating such profits. The definition does, however, take into account the diversity of returns and the potential diversity and eclecticism of employee contributions. Competitive salaries, pay increases, merit incentives, and indirect forms of compensation such as compensatory time off are a few examples of rewards (Mahaney and Lederer, 2006). Offering workers a wage premium a payment that is more than what other employers would pay for equivalent work can help firms enhance worker productivity. A wage premium could enhance productivity by improving nutrition, encouraging greater adherence to company goals, boosting morale, lowering quits and the disruption caused by turnover, luring in higher-quality workers, and inspiring workers to exert more effort (Goldsmith et al., 2000). As a result, people are driven to profitable occupations, work harder

to complete tasks that will enhance their salary, and become angry if their pay is jeopardized or decreased (Stajkovic and Luthans, 2016). Financial rewards are one method to show that a company is serious about rewarding team efforts to improve quality. Each member of the team will be given a cash bonus as part of the financial rewards. The bonus would be given separately from the salary in addition to the compensation. However, it's crucial to use team rewards in a way that doesn't undercut employees' motivation to do a good job. Employee innovation is crucial to the continuous improvement process since it results in better business operations or contented customers.

According to Balkin et al. (1997), the use of extrinsic rewards that are closely related to team project management performance may encourage team members to become money-hungry and weaken their intrinsic motivation for the work itself. Extrinsic benefits may be financial or non-financial. Usually, the monetary compensation is a separate variable payment from the salary. It can be given individually or in a group setting as a reward for exceptional project management performance or as an encouragement. The prerequisites for receiving this incentive must be established in advance, and project management success must be quantifiable. In order for a reward system to be truly motivating, the reward must meet a number of requirements: it must be valuable, significant enough to have an impact, understandable, timely, have a lasting effect, and be cost-effective (Merchant, 2007). According to Lawler and Moss (2017), the business must install a PA system if the compensation system is intended to distribute rewards in proportion to variances in project management success. Managers will be able to recognize top performers and praise them, as well as those staff members who have room for advancement. If an appraisal is tied to a reward and remuneration system that employees do not trust or support, it would not be effective (Stockley, 2019). Only if regular reviews are conducted in their favor, if they are involved in setting goals for project management success payments like commissions and bonuses, and if pay policies are fully disclosed will employees support the incentive system. Their morale will be raised, and they'll always look forward to going to work and giving selflessly to the organization. People value money, making it a key kind of compensation, claims Merchant (2007). The three main types of financial reward systems are project management success-based compensation increases, short-term incentive plans, and long-term incentive plans.

The latter two rewards are common at the managerial levels and are typically linked to effective project management over a specific period of time. It's common perception that the first one has the strongest motivational power. He goes on to argue that every company boosts wages for employees at all organizational levels. Although this is typically a modest fraction of an employee's income, it has a substantial value due to its long-term perspective. Organizations frequently use some types of short-term rewards. A monetary incentive is typically based on project management performance measured over a time period of one year or less (Merchant, 2007). A corporation utilizes variable pay primarily to distinguish it among the workforce so that the most productive workers are rewarded. They add that acknowledging an employee's contributions to the business makes it simpler for the business to support successful project management. They assert further that employees cherish the possibility of receiving remuneration for managing projects successfully. In terms of risk-sharing, the use of variable

compensation may be advantageous to the business. This shows that when a portion of the compensation is variable, the expense for compensation varies more depending on how well the company manages its projects, with the cost being lower when a profit is not made and higher when a profit can be distributed to the employees. Project management performance measurements across time intervals greater than a year are used to determine long-term incentive payments. By doing this, a business can enhance the long-term worth of the organization by rewarding people for their exceptional work and project management performance (Kreitner & Kinicki, 2014).

Additionally, this helps attract and keep critical talent. A very popular type of long-term reward is a restricted stock plan, in one form or another. This incentive is given to the employee in the form of shares, but they cannot be sold until the specified time has passed. For instance, after a year, the employee was allowed to sell one-fifth of the shares, two after two years, three after three years, etc. As they will lose the remaining benefits if they opt to leave their jobs before the fifth year, this is a tactic to keep knowledge within the company rather than to motivate employees. Some companies take things a step further and return the shares you've already received. Additional decisions may be made on supplemental payments linked to skill or project management performance, such as overtime, risk or "dirt money," shift premiums, bonuses, or commissions, in addition to basic pay. According to dominant reward language, supplemental payments that are integrated into base payments are classified as contingent pay, whereas payments that are not consolidated are classified as base pay components (Armstrong, 2020).

While some employee rewards are provided by the company, according to Doyle (2020), neither the employer nor the employee is required to do so. They are covered by the collective bargaining agreement and offered at the employer's option. They are different across organizations; a few examples are hazard pay, health insurance, maternity, paternity, adoption leaves, paid holidays, salary increases, severance pay, sick days, terminations, vacation days, and work breaks. Employers must therefore have workers' compensation insurance coverage. One of the benefits is compensation for missed pay and medical expenditures. They are paid to the employees in installments, normally at a rate of two-thirds of the pay. The organization should also sponsor disability programs for the employees. It ought to offer expanded disability protection.

According to Donata (2011), some companies should offer social security disability benefits. One must, however, have held social security-covered employment. Wright et al. (2020) suggested grouping these benefits into the following four categories: incentives linked to employment status or seniority, such as company cars, vacation days, and sabbaticals; benefits relating to personal security and health, such as sick pay, loans for medical bills, and life insurance; family-friendly incentives include child care facilities, nursery coupons, and improved maternity, paternity, and parental leave regulations; Social, 'goodwill', or lifestyle advantages, such as subsidized canteens, gyms, sports facilities, special offers, and dry cleaners.

He also suggests that these benefits may be elective, giving employees the freedom to "opt-in" or "opt-out" of them in accordance with their financial situations and personal desires. If employees choose to purchase benefits like daycare vouchers, loans under the circle-to-work plan, life insurance, or pension contributions, agreements are typically made for at-source deductions to take place. This may result in tax benefits for the employees. Some businesses have modified their project management success appraisal processes to put more emphasis on training staff members for future improvement. Even the decision to promote is based on quality achievements. Employees who have performed well typically feel a sense of success and self-worth when they receive rewards that are unrelated to money or pay-related matters (Allen and Kilmann, 2016; Omran et al., 2011). On the basis of the debate above, the following theory is put forth:

3. RESEARCH METHOD

A questionnaire was developed from previous studies and distributed among the respondents via online and by hand survey and the response time was two months. In two months the online survey was observed carefully and then data was collected after securitization. The target population was the employees who were involved in the construction industry sector in Libya. As employees working in the construction industry comprise many departments, thus, the population was restricted to all the executive employees who are directly linked to management.

The sample consists of employees who are highly qualified and handling the management of the construction industry. Purposive sampling was employed as a sampling technique for this study. Purposive sampling, according to Trochim & Donnelly (2008), is a research methodology that enlists members of predetermined groups that are relevant to a certain study. The minimal sample size for this study was 205 employees (based on a 1% significance level with a minimum r^2 of 0.10) working at various construction companies operating in Libya.

This was done taking into account the general rule of thumb and keeping in mind the unknown overall population. To achieve this target, a total of 10 construction companies were selected randomly for data collection, and to ensure the minimum required samples, 50% more questionnaires were distributed among the different branches just to make sure the sample size was more than the required minimum sample size. Hence, the target sample size for this study was between 250 – 400 employees.

The data was collected from employees working in the construction industry in Libya. For the purpose of the study, the researchers used a survey method since many of the employees are very busy and cannot be easily accessed. The researchers obtained an approval letter from the university, specifically the office (postgraduate and research office). The questionnaire with its items was distributed to the respondents by hand as well as online. The respondents were instructed to encircle the option on the questionnaire pages. After indicating their respective thought or perceptions by putting a circle, they were required to return the questionnaire. Next, numerical numbers were assigned to the responses and input into the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) software version 22.0 for the analyses.

4. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Respondents' Background

Table 1 presents the background characteristics of the participating respondents, including gender, race, age, educational level, working experience, and job title. The total frequency of males is 203 (65.5%) and that of females is 107 (34.5%). In terms of race, 211 (68.1%) out of 310 were Libyans. As per the participants' age, only 20 % were aged between 25-30 years old while 38.7 % were aged above 40 years old. Education level is high in Libya; overall, 59 percent of the respondents hold a bachelor's degree, 33.5 percent have a master's degree, and 7.5 percent of them hold a doctorate. In terms of working experience, 67 (21.6%) have working experience of less than 5 years but the majority number 174 (56.1%) are having a working experience of more than 10 years. Out of the 310 respondents, 144 (46.5%) hold a managerial post and 82 (26.5%) hold an executive post.

Table 1: Shows the respondents' background

	Frequency	Percent
Gender		
Male	203	65.5%
Female	107	34.5%
Total	310	100%
Race		
Libyan	211	68.1%
Asia	55	17.7%
African	17	5.5%
Other	27	8.7%
Total	310	100%
Age		
25-30 years	62	20
30-35 years	58	18.7
35-40 years	70	22.6
Above 40 years	120	38.7
Total	310	100
Level of Education		
Bachelors	183	59
Masters	104	33.5
PhD	23	7.4
Total	310	100
Working Experience		
Less than 5 years	67	21.6
5-10 years	69	22.3
More than 10 years	174	56.1
Total	310	100
Job title		
Junior	25	8.1%
Executive	82	26.5%
Managerial	144	46.5%
Director	24	7.7%
Other	35	11.3%
Total	310	100%

4.2 Relationship between rewards and compensation and employee engagement

The statistical indicator of how closely the data resemble the fitted regression line is called R-squared. For multiple regression, it is sometimes referred to as the coefficient of determination or the coefficient of multiple determination. As shown in Table 2, it can be revealed that the R square value is 0.372 which means the percentage of the variability for R square is 37.2% between the dependent and independent variables, i.e. employee engagement & rewards and compensation.

Table 2: Shows the relationship between rewards and compensation with employee engagement

Model Summary ^b									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.610 ^a	.372	.370	.57295	.372	182.800	1	308	.000
a. Predictors: (Constant), AVG_RWC									
b. Dependent Variable: AVG_EE									

In regression results, ANOVA is the most important part which explains the acceptance and rejection of the hypothesis. The standard significant level for research is 0.05 ($p < 0.05$); if the significant value is less than 0.05, then, the hypothesis will be accepted, otherwise, rejected. As depicted in Table 3, it can be noticed that $p < 0.05$ which indicates that the hypothesis is accepted.

Table 3: Shows the ANOVA results

ANOVA ^a								
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.		
1	Regression	60.008	1	60.008	182.800	.000 ^b		
	Residual	101.108	308	.328				
	Total	161.116	309					
a. Dependent Variable: AVG_EE								
b. Predictors: (Constant), AVG_RWC								
Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	1.100	.103		10.686	.000		
	AVG_RWC	.605	.045	.610	13.520	.000	1.000	1.000
a. Dependent Variable: AVG_EE								

The hypothesis is accepted when the t-values for rewards and compensation (R&C) and constant are large (13.520 and 10.686, respectively), with a tiny p-value of 0.00 indicating that the means are significantly different. We would claim that the means are significantly different because the hypothesis is accepted by a large F (182.800) and a small p-value. A large F and a low p-value indicate that the hypothesis is accepted, and we would claim that the response and predictors generally have a relationship. The value of the path regression coefficient of zero

means the hypothesis is accepted, while the opposite is the rejected one. The hypothesis is accepted if the t value is high and the p-value is low, in which case we would claim that the regression coefficient is not 0. The hypothesis's beta value of 0.610 indicates that reward and compensation (R&C) contribute 61% to employee engagement (EE). According to Cascio (2010), there have been three significant shifts in company pay and benefits policies. Some of these include the implementation of performance rewarding programs, which makes pay more variable, as well as an increased desire to scale down workforce size, outsource jobs, and limit pay to control costs of benefits and wages/salaries. In addition, there has been a shift away from focusing on what competitors are paying in favor of what the company can afford.

Rewards are things that can be considered a return to workers for exhibiting desirable behavior; they could range from healthcare benefits or a cash bonus to involvement in decision-making, autonomy, increased role responsibility, and other benefits. Hence, the definition of rewards is one beyond the definitions of remuneration, compensation, and benefits terminology that focus on pay and other monetized agreements. Every organization has a reward system in place. UNDP research from 2018 states that reward and incentive systems are crucial for building capacities and converting those capacities into better motivation and engagement. According to the report, a reward and engagement-based policy with a financial element would draw management talent by offering incentives that would inspire a bigger number of employees. These benefits may be granted in a variety of ways, including stock options, profit-sharing plans, and recognition programs, among others. Profit sharing, according to Lusthaus et al. (2002), is a tactic for allocating a pool of funds for employee distribution by taking a predetermined portion of a company's profits. This program's goal is to give employees recognition for their contributions to the company's attained profit target. Higher productivity and lower employee turnover are just two examples of how devoted employees give businesses important competitive advantages. Therefore, according to Vance (2018), it is not unexpected that businesses of all sizes and types have made significant investments in the policies and procedures that encourage employee engagement and dedication. Even while different firms define engagement in different ways, there are certain common aspects; these include the degree to which people genuinely believe in their work, the belief that their employer values the contributions they make, and the contentment with and pride in their employer among the workers. If a worker is more engaged, they are more likely to "go the extra mile" and do well at work. Additionally, motivated employees may be more devoted to remaining with their current employers. It is obvious that dedication and involvement have the ability to result in positive business outcomes for a company (Vance, 2018). In conclusion, the following can be stated about the hypothesis testing:

H1: Rewards and Compensation have positive impact on employee engagement.

Figure 1: Proposed Framework for the Study

5. IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

This study is one of the very few studies conducted in the Arab world to examine such relationships between rewards and compensation on employee engagement. Hence, it is attempted to add to the existing knowledge by examining and understanding the impact of this independent variable (reward and compensation) on employee engagement as the dependent variable, then the impact of employee engagement on project management success. It can be said that the study has some contribution to both academia and practice, whereas it contributes to academics by attempting to increase the understanding of the importance of the relationship between rewards and compensation and employee engagement.

A study model was developed using data from prior investigations, from which hypotheses were formulated and tested. In general, the model has been empirically supported, which improves our theoretical understanding. The study as a whole has made contributions to the literature by providing an in-depth understanding of the linkages between rewards and compensation, employee engagement, and other factors that have been studied in many studies and contexts and have been examined together in the context of Libya. It also demonstrates the importance of rewards and compensation and employee engagement. An effective project manager is able to meet or exceed stakeholder expectations while meeting project objectives within the constraints of time, budget, and scope. As a contribution to policymakers, the present study's results have implications for construction authority, decision-makers, and policy planners. It raises the issue of employee engagement and performance of organizations which are the most important matters of any organization in Libya. In addition, the impacts of rewards and compensation on employee engagement toward project management success were examined. There are several ways in which project management success can influence policymakers at various levels, including local, regional, and national levels. In turn, policymakers are better able to meet their responsibilities to taxpayers and stakeholders through the promotion of accountability and transparency. Policymakers can use effective project management to allocate resources, prioritize projects, and manage risks in a timely and accurate way.

6. CONCLUSION

To sum up, this paper investigated the impact of rewards and compensation and employee engagement on project management success in the construction industry within Libya. The total valid questionnaires were 310 collected from construction industry authorities. Outstandingly, the results found that rewards and compensation have a significant positive impact on employee engagement and there is a significant positive impact of employee engagement on project management success. This study has made some recommendations for future research opportunities:

- A case study method may be taken in the future to help people understand the steps and mechanisms involved in achieving organizational success and employee engagement. Researchers can understand the intricate relationships between the variables using this method.
- It is clear from the generated literature that there are various components that affect employee engagement and project management success, including the independent variable of the study; for deeper insight, other variables should also be tested.
- The absence of a few frameworks in Libya compels to ponder for different strategies to improve the system of employee engagement and carry it to the front for implementation; these strategies can be attained by adding more variables and case studies.

Reference

- 1) Allen, R.S., & Kilmann, R.H. (2001). The Role of the Reward System for a Total Quality Management-Based Strategy. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 14(2), 110-131.
- 2) Allen, R.S., & Kilmann, R.H. (2001). The role of the reward system for a total quality management based strategy. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 14(2): 110-131.
- 3) Anita, R., Abdillah, M.R., Wu, W., Sapthiarsyah, M. F., & Sari, R. N. (2020). Married Female Employees' Work-Life Balance and Job Performance: The Role of Affective Commitment. *Pertanika J. Soc. Sci. Humanit*, 28, 1787-1806.
- 4) Anitha, J. (2014). Determinants of employee engagement and their impact on employee performance. *International Journal Prod Perform Management*, 63(3):308–323.
- 5) Armstrong, M. (2018). *A Hand Book of Human Resource Management Practice*, 10th Edition London: Kogan Page.
- 6) Attridge, M. (2009). Measuring and managing employee work engagement: A review of the research and business literature. *Journal of Workplace Behavioral Health*, 24(4), 383–398.
- 7) Attridge, M. (2019). A global perspective on promoting workplace mental health and the role of employee assistance programs. *American Journal of Health Promotion*, 33(4), 622-629.
- 8) Bakker, A.B., & Demerouti, E. (2018). Multiple levels in job demands-resources theory: Implications for employee well-being and performance. In Diener E., Oishi S., Tay L. (Eds.), *Handbook of well-being* (pp. 593–604).
- 9) Balkin, D., Dolan, S., & Forgues, K. (1997). Rewards for team contributions to quality. *Document de recherche*, (97-03).

- 10) Bandura, A. (2018), "An agentic perspective on positive psychology", in Lopez, S.J. (Ed.), *Positive Psychology*, Vol. 1, Greenwood, Westport, CT, pp. 167-196.
- 11) Bloom, M., & Milkovich, G.T. (1998). Relationships among risk, incentive pay, and organizational performance. *Academy of Management Journal*, 41(3): 283-297.
- 12) Cascio W. F. (2010). *Managing human resources: productivity, quality of work life, profits.* (8th Ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill.
- 13) Cascio, W.F. (2003). Changes in workers, work, and organizations. *Handbook of psychology*, 12, 401-422.
- 14) Donata, L.E.V.I. (2011). ICT and Art Heritage: a Project of the University of Udine for the Dissemination of Knowledge. *The New Technologies for Aquileia 2011*: 1-
- 15) Doyle, O. (2020). COVID-19: Exacerbating educational inequalities. *Public Policy*, 9, 1-10.
- 16) Echols, M.E. (2015). Engaging Employee to Impact Performances. *Chief Learning Officer*, 4(2): 44-48.
- 17) Fobiri, G., Musonda, I., & Muleya, F. (2022). Reality capture in Construction Project Management: A review of opportunities and challenges. *Buildings*, 12(9): 1381.
- 18) Gerald, S. (2011). *Rewards and Job Commitment of Primary School Teachers in Mityana District, Uganda.* Unpublished Masters of Educational Management Project, Makerere University.
- 19) Goldsmith, A.H., Veum, J.R., & Darity Jr, W. (2000). Working hard for the money? Efficiency wages and worker effort. *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 21(4): 351-385.
- 20) Gupta, M., & Shukla, K. (2018). An empirical clarification on the assessment of engagement at work. *Advances in Developing Human Resources*, 20(1): 44-57.
- 21) Kerzner, H. (2019). *Using the Project Management Maturity Model: Strategic Planning For Project Management.* John Wiley & Sons.
- 22) Kreitner, A., & Kinicki, A. (2014). *Organizational behavior.* Boston, MA: McGraw-Hill Irwin.
- 23) Lawler, E.E. III. (1971). *Pay and organizational effectiveness: A psychological view.* New York: McGraw-Hill.
- 24) Lawless, J., & Moss, C. (2017). Exploring the value of dignity in the work-life of nurses. *Contemporary Nurse*, 24(2): 225-236.
- 25) Lee, J., & Ok, C.M. (2016). Hotel employee work engagement and its consequences. *Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management*, 25(2): 133-166.
- 26) Leiter, M.P., & Maslach, C. (2016). Latent burnout profiles: A new approach to understanding the burnout experience. *Burnout Research*, 3(4): 89-100.
- 27) Loufrani-Fedida, S., & Missonier, D. (2015). The Project Manager Cannot Be A Hero Anymore! Understanding Critical Competencies in Project-Based Organizations from a Multilevel Approach. *International Journal of Project Management*, 33(6): 1220-1235.
- 28) Lusthaus, C., Adriene, M., Anderson, G., Carden, F., & Plinio Montalvan, G. (2002). *Organisational Assessment: A Framework for Improving Performance.* Ottawa, Canada: International Development Research Centre, 80.
- 29) Luthans, F., & Peterson, S.J. (2002). Employee engagement and manager self-efficacy. *Journal of Management Development*, 21(5): 376-387.
- 30) MacLeod, D., & Clarke, N. (2010). Leadership and employee engagement: passing fad or a new way of doing business? *International Journal of Leadership in Public Services*, 6(4): 26-30.

- 31) Macy, W.H., & Schneider, B. (2018). The Meaning of Employee Engagement. *Industrial and Organisational Psychology*, 1, 3-30.
- 32) Mahoney, R.C., & Lederer, A.L. (2006). The effect of intrinsic and extrinsic rewards for developers on information systems project success. *Project Management Journal*, 37(4): 42-55.
- 33) Manas, T., & Graham, M. (2003). *Creating a Total Rewards Strategy: A Toolkit for Designing*. Washington, American Management Association.
- 34) Markos, S., & Sandhya Sridevi, M. (2010). Employee Engagement: The Key to Improving Performance. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 5(12): 89-96.
- 35) McEwen, K., & Boyd, C.M. (2018). A measure of team resilience: Developing the resilience at work team scale. *Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 60(3): 258-272.
- 36) Merchant, V.D.S. (2007). *Management Control System, performance measurement, Evaluation and Incentive*, New York: Financial Times/Prentice.
- 37) Meredith, P., & Mantel, T. (2021). *Project Management: A Managerial Approach*. Hoboken, NJ, USA: Wiley.
- 38) Mohd Nasurdin, A., Tan, C.L., & Naseer Khan, S. (2020). Can high performance work practices and satisfaction predict job performance? An examination of the Malaysian private health-care sector. *International Journal of Quality and Service Sciences*, 12(4): 521-540.
- 39) Omran, A., & Jarmajo, S. (2015). Barriers Affecting the Project Managers 'competencies in the Nigerian Construction Industry. *Journal of Academic Research in Economics*, 7(1): 154-163.
- 40) Omran, A., & Zaid, H. (2014). Determining Factors Affecting Safety Performance Practices of Construction Contractors in Gaza Strip, Palestine. *Journal of Academic Research in Economics*, 6(3):350-360.
- 41) Omran, A., Hammad, M.S., & Pakir, A.K. (2011). Factors Affecting Productivity in the Libyan Construction Projects: A Case Study. *Journal of Academic Research in Economics*, 3(1): 77-88.
- 42) Rama Devi, V. (2009). Employee engagement is a two-way street. *Human Resource Management International Digest*, 17(2): 3-4.
- 43) Rehman, M.Z., Khan, M.R., & Lashari, Z.A. (2010). Effect of Job Rewards on Job Satisfaction, Moderating role of Age Differences: An Empirical Evidence From. *African Journal of Business Management*, 1131-1139.
- 44) Saks, A.M., & Gruman, J.A. (2018). Socialization resources theory and newcomers' work engagement: A new pathway to newcomer socialization. *Career Development International*, 23(1): 12-32.
- 45) Saudah, S., & Azis, M. (2019). Sharia Mutual Fund Performance, Foreign Ownership and Investment Ability. *AFEBI Islamic Finance and Economic Review*, 4(02): 140-149.
- 46) Stajkovic, A.D., & Luthans, F. (2019). Behavioral Management and Task Performance in Organizations: Conceptual Background, Meta-analysis, and Test of Alternative Models, *Personnel Psychology*, 56, 155-194.
- 47) Storm, K., & Rothmann, S. (2003). A psychometric analysis of the Utrecht Work Engagement Scale in the South African police service. *SA Journal of Industrial Psychology*, 29(4), 62-70.
- 48) Swaminathan and Rajasekaran (2010). Essential Components of Employee Engagement – A study with Reference to TNSTC Kumbakonam. *Advance in Management*, 3(12):55-59.
- 49) Thakur, P. (2014). A Research paper on the Effect of Employee Engagement on Job Satisfaction in its Sector. *Journal of Business Management & Social Sciences Research*, 3(5), 31-39.

- 50) Tian, Q., & Robertson, J.L. (2019). How And When Does Perceived CSR Affect Employees' Engagement In Voluntary Pro-Environmental Behavior? *Journal of Business Ethics*, 155, 399-412.
- 51) Trochim, W.M.K., & Donnelly, J.P. (2008). *The Research Methods Knowledge Base*. 3rd Edition, atomic Dog, Mason, 56-65.
- 52) Vance, R.J. (2018). Employee Engagement and Commitment: A guide to understanding, measuring and increasing engagement in your organization, SHRM Foundation's Effective Practice Guidelines, SHRM Foundation.
- 53) Welbourne, T.M. (2017). Employee engagement: Beyond the fad and into the executive suite, *Leader to leader*, 44, 45-51.
- 54) Woodruff, D. (2018). *Money unmade: Barter and the fate of Russian capitalism*. Cornell University Press.
- 55) Wright, A.L., Sonin, K., Driscoll, J., & Wilson, J. (2020). Poverty and economic dislocation reduce compliance with COVID-19 shelter-in-place protocols. *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization*, 180, 544-554.